

Disease brief_Influenza in Swine

	Characteristics	Description
1	Disease and Pathogen	<p>Influenza in swine is a highly contagious viral respiratory infection of pigs. Influenza in swine is caused by influenza A viruses, which are further characterized by subtypes namely H1N1, H1N2 and H3N2 (12).</p> <p>Swine influenza viruses (SIV) do not normally infect humans, however, sporadic human infections with influenza viruses that normally infect swine have occurred. Most commonly, human infections with variant viruses have occurred in people exposed to infected pigs (e.g., children near pigs at a fair or workers in the swine industry) (1)</p>
2	Regulatory status in the EU	Influenza in swine is a non-WOAH-listed disease. Influenza in swine is listed in Dir 2003/99/EC (in Annex I -point B – “List of zoonoses and zoonotic agents to be monitored according to the epidemiological situation”). Notification may be required in individual Member States.
3	Geographical distribution (of autochthonous cases)	<p>Influenza in swine is common in Europe, North and South America, and parts of Asia. It has been reported in Africa as well (12).</p> <p>Surveillance in 17 countries targeted to pig farms where acute respiratory symptoms were observed resulted in 30.5% of herds examined as positive (3).</p>
4	Reservoir / main host	<p><i>Suidae</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • domestic pigs (<i>Sus scrofa domesticus</i>) • wild boar (<i>Sus scrofa</i>) <p><i>Suidae</i> are also susceptible to infections with both avian and human influenza A viruses and can play a role in interspecies transmission. This could result in co-infection and genetic reassortment of viruses of swine, human or avian origin.</p>
5	Host range / susceptible species (domestic / wild)	Birds and humans are susceptible to infections with swine, avian and human influenza A viruses.
6	Vector-borne transmission	No.

7	Environmental transmission	No.
8	(Main) transmission routes to domestic animals	Mostly, if not exclusively via the respiratory route (contact or aerosol). Influenza A viruses (both seasonal human influenza strains and the pandemic A(H1N1)pdm09 strain) can be transmitted from humans to pigs (5).
9	(Main) transmission routes to humans	Direct close or indirect contact with infected pigs (10). Human infections with swine influenza viruses are occasionally reported, usually in occupationally exposed groups (12). Influenza viruses in swine spread very rarely in human populations. There has been some evidence of limited (sporadic) person-to-person transmission of H3N2v but none for sustained human-to-human transmission.
10	Disease indicators	Mainly coughing pigs with fever.
11	a) Clinical signs	Influenza in swine is a disease of the respiratory tract with typically sudden onset of symptoms. General signs include anorexia, inactivity, fever, respiratory distress, coughing, conjunctivitis, nasal discharge and weight loss (6). The duration of the incubation period is 1–3 days, with rapid recovery 5–7 days after onset. This herd disease is characterized by high morbidity and low mortality (2). Disease severity depends on the age of the pigs and the size and density of the population on the farm. The most severe symptoms including fever, inappetence, coughing and severe dyspnoea may be recorded in fattening pigs who experience a first SIV infection in the second half of the fattening period. Secondary bacterial infections can lead to a prolonged course of disease. Morbidity approaches 100 % and mortality 2–3 %. Recovery typically follows after 4–7 days (2).
	b) Shedding/ detectability of pathogen	Virus replication is generally limited to epithelial cells of the upper and lower respiratory tract of pigs (nasal mucosa, tonsils, trachea and lungs). SIV is exclusively excreted and transmitted via the respiratory route. Infectious virus can be isolated from the tissues of the respiratory tract, from bronchoalveolar lavage fluid, and nasal, tonsillar or oropharyngeal swabs. Experimental studies showed that SIV can be isolated 1 – 7 days post infection. Spread to other organ systems is unlikely and there is generally no detectable viraemia. SIV shedding is in general associated with symptoms (11). Secondary infection with other viruses or bacteria can lead to a prolonged course of disease, but without increasing the period of virus shedding.

12	b) Seroconversion	Seroconversion is rarely seen in SIV-naive pigs. A significant rise in pre-existing antibody titres can only be noted after consecutive inoculations with different strains. Antibodies show limited cross-reaction to other subtype(s) (9).
13	c) Other disease indicators	See clinical signs.
14	Indicators relevant for monitoring (Indicator-based surveillance)	Respiratory symptoms, fever and general signs as anorexia, inactivity, or weight loss.
15	Test systems available for infection/disease detection	<p>Identification of the agent</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standard: real time RT-PCR. Real-time RT-PCR assays are described to be more sensitive than conventional RT-PCR (3). • Culture of clinical material in cells or embryonated fowl's eggs. • Virus characterization can be achieved by a range of tools, including standard typing through haemagglutination inhibition test (HI) and/or RT-PCR or genome sequencing. <p>Real time RT-PCRs based on the matrix (M) or the nucleoprotein (NP) gene, covering all influenza A viruses known to be endemic in European pigs and emergent strains from North America, are available (2).</p> <p>Serological tests</p> <p>Hemagglutination inhibition (HI) assays to determine the HI titres antibodies.</p>
16	Surveillance component options (+ rationale)	<p>1. Pathogen detection and genetic characterization in pigs with clinical signs.</p> <p>Rationale: Clinical signs are the earliest detectable indicator of SI infection. Clinical signs are generally associated with SIV shedding. Shedding pigs pose a risk to human health.</p> <p>Alternatives surveillance components (not described in detail): Testing of wild boars and feral pigs. Wild boars and feral pigs are under-investigated hosts for influenza A viruses. Literature shows evidence that the same viral genotypes circulate in both pigs and wild boars living in the same geographical area (4; 7; 8).</p> <p>Influenza in swine may pose a risk for endangered wildlife species in Europe. Among wild endangered species distributed in Europe potentially infected by Influenza in swine (diagnosis includes direct</p>

- 3) ESNIP (European Surveillance Network for Influenza in Pigs), 2013. Project 259949 – Final Technical Report (December 2013). Available online: <https://cordis.europa.eu/docs/results/259/259949/final1-template-for-final-report-esnip-3-.pdf>.
- 4) Foni E, Garbarino C, Chiapponi C, Baioni L, Zanni I and Cordioli P, 2013. Epidemiological survey of Influenza in swine A virus in the wild boar population of two Italian provinces. *Influenza Other Respiratory Viruses*, 7 Suppl 4,16-20. doi: 10.1111/irv.12198. PMID: 24224815; PMCID: PMC5655886.
- 5) Nelson MI, Gramer MR, Vincent AL and Holmes EC, 2012. Global transmission of influenza viruses from humans to swine. *Journal of General Virology*, 93, 2195–2203.
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- 7) Schülein A, Ritzmann M, Christian J, Schneider K and Neubauer-Juric A, 2021. Exposure of wild boar to Influenza A viruses in Bavaria: Analysis of seroprevalences and antibody subtype specificity before and after the panzootic of highly pathogenic avian influenza viruses A (H5N8). *Zoonoses Public Health*, 68(5), 503-515. doi: 10.1111/zph.12841. Epub 2021 May 13. PMID: 33987931.
- 8) Shimoda H, VAN Nguyen D, Yonemitsu K, Minami S, Nagata N, Hara N, Kuwata R, Murakami S, Koder Y, Takeda T, Yoshikawa Y, Horimoto T and Maeda K, 2017. Influenza A virus infection in Japanese wild boars (*Sus scrofa leucomystax*). *The Journal of veterinary medical science*, 79(5), 848-851. doi: 10.1292/jvms.17-0052.
- 9) Van Reeth K, Labarque G and Pensaert M, 2006. Serological profiles after consecutive experimental infections of pigs with European H1N1, H3N2, and H1N2 swine influenza viruses. *Viral Immunology*, 19, 373–82. Erratum in *Viral Immunology*, 19, 775.
- 10) Van Reeth K, 2007. Avian and swine influenza viruses: our current understanding of the zoonotic risk. *Veterinary Research*, 38, 243–260.
- 11) Van Reeth K and Ma W, 2012. Swine influenza virus vaccines: to change or not to change—that's the question. *Current Topics in Microbiology And immunology*, 370, 173–200.
- 12) WOAH (World Organisation for Animal Health), 2009. Swine influenza. OIE Technical Disease Card. Available online:

		<p>https://www.woah.org/fileadmin/Home/eng/Animal_Health_in_the_World/docs/pdf/Disease_cards/SWINE_INFLUENZA.pdf.</p> <p>13) ENETWILD-consortium, Klaas, Marina, Sebastian, Mario, Ferroglio, Ezio, Goncalves, Catarina, Vada, Rachele, Vicente, Joaquín, Zanet, Stefania, Dolores-Gavier-Widén, , Vicente, Joaquín. 2022. A review of endangered wildlife hosts in Europe for selected pathogens to be targeted by One Health surveillance. EFSA Supporting publication 2022: 19(12):EN-7766. 12 pp. doi:10.2903/sp.efsa.2022.EN-7766</p>
20	Additional comments	<p>If positive pig samples are sequenced, a better understanding in genotypes and subtypes circulating within the country can be gained, including how animal genome sequences relate to human cases.</p> <p>Sampling of pig producers with flu-like symptoms will aid the detection of possible virus transmission between human and pigs and identification of co-infection and genetic reassortment.</p>